

INFLUENCE OF LAMINATE CONSTITUTION ON IMPACT STRENGTH OF C/A HYBRID UNIDIRECTIONAL FRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon/aramid (C/A) hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates were prepared in which the volume ratio of CFRP to AFRP was 50 % to 50 % and in which the thickness of repeating unit of CFRP and AFRP were varied. Then the impact bending tests of these C/A hybrid FRP laminates were conducted as well as the static bending tests. As the results, it was cleared that the static and impact flexural strengths of C/A hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates depend fairly well on the laminate constitution, and that the laminate constitution which maximizes the flexural strength exists.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the advanced fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) of which the fibers are carbon and aramid fibers are used as the structure components of spaceship etc. These fibers do not hold all of the excellent mechanical properties such as high elastic modulus, high tensile strength and high ultimate strain, although each fiber has the remarkable mechanical properties. For example, high modulus carbon fibers hold high modulus but low ultimate strain, high strength carbon fibers hold high tensile strength and aramid fibers hold high ultimate strain^{1,2}. Thus hybrid FRP consisting of plural type fibers having different mechanical properties have attracted large interests for satisfying specially required mechanical properties. There are many papers reported on the static tensile, flexural, fatigue and impact properties of the unidirectionally reinforced laminated hybrid FRP^{3,4}. And the law of mixture based on the volume fraction of each fiber is found to be applicable to the stress-strain relation^{5,6}. However, the simple law of mixture does not always apply in terms of fracture strength under any type of load. The mechanism of reinforcement in hybrid FRP has not been clarified yet.

In this paper, carbon/aramid (C/A) hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates were prepared in which the volume ratio of CFRP to AFRP was 50 % to 50 % and in which the thickness of repeating unit of CFRP and AFRP were varied. Then the impact bending tests of these C/A hybrid FRP laminates were conducted as well as the static bending tests. The influence of the laminate constitution on these strength are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

PREPARATION OF SPECIMENS

The two kinds of fibers were prepared. One is the carbon fibers, BESFIGHT 6000 made by Toho Rayon Ltd. and the other is the aramid fibers, KEVLAR 49 made by Du Pont Co. Ltd. The formations and properties of these fibers are tabulated on Table I. The laminated plates were molded by compression forming of the prepreg sheets of epoxy resin (thickness 0.2 mm) in which the fibers of carbon or aramid were

unidirectionally arranged. These laminated plates are carbon, aramid and C/A hybrid FRP plates reinforced unidirectionally. The laminated number of prepreg sheets is 15 and the thickness of plates is 3 mm shown in Fig. 1. The surfaces of specimens of A and C series in this figure are respectively CFRP and AFRP layers. The number of layers in a repeating unit in both series are 1,2,3 and 4 respectively. The volume fraction of fibers in CFRP and AFRP layers in these plates is approximately 60 %.

TEST PROCEDURES

The static and impact three points bending tests were carried out by using the specimens of which the thickness, width and length are 3 mm, 10 mm and 100 mm respectively. The span is 60 mm. The electro-hydraulic servo machine and the electronic measuring Charpy testing machine were used for static and impact tests respectively, on which the cross head speeds were 20 mm/min and 1.2x10³ mm/min (2mm/sec).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

LOAD-DEFLECTION DIAGRAMS

The load-deflection diagrams of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP in Fig.1 on static and impact tests are shown in Fig.2. The diagrams on the impact tests are very similar to those on the static tests for each laminate constitution of specimens. The diagrams of CFRP are roughly linear until maximum load. On the other hand, the diagrams of AFRP curve remarkably beyond knee point although these diagrams are roughly linear until knee point.

The diagrams of C series are roughly linear until the maximum loads as well as those of CFRP, although the loads don't become suddenly to zero after the maximum loads. The diagrams of A series show slightly the nonlinear behavior until the maximum load which are not so remarkable comparing with that on the diagrams of AFRP.

FLEXURAL STRENGTH, ULTIMATE STRAIN AND ABSORBED ENERGY

The flexural strengths σ_b , the ultimate strains ϵ_b , the energies to peak load E_p and the energies after peak load E_a respectively are obtained by substituting F_b , δ_b , A_p and A_a shown in Fig.3 into the following equations.

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3 \cdot F_b \cdot l}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2} \quad (1) \quad , \quad \epsilon_b = \frac{6 \cdot h \cdot \delta_b}{l^2} \quad (2)$$

$$E_a = \frac{A_a}{b \cdot h} \quad (3) \quad , \quad E_p = \frac{A_p}{b \cdot h} \quad (4)$$

where, l : span, b : width of specimen, h : thickness of specimen.

The flexural strengths σ_b and the ultimate strains ϵ_b of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP by static and impact test are shown in Fig.4 and the energies to peak load E_p and the energies after peak load E_a of those FRP are also shown in Fig.5. σ_b , ϵ_b and E_p on the impact load are almost equal to those on the static load except the specimens of A-2, A-3 and A-4. σ_b , ϵ_b , E_p and E_a change remarkably with laminate constitution, and static and impact flexural strength σ_b are maximized on the laminate constitution of A-3 that the thickness of repeating unit equals 0.6 mm in A series. These values are almost equivalent to the static and impact flexural strengths of CFRP.

The ultimate strains of C series on the static and impact loads do not change with laminate constitution and these values are almost equivalent to those of CFRP. On the other hand, the ultimate strains of A series vary monotonously with the laminate constitution from A-1 to A-4 and are maximized on the laminate constitution of A-4, on which the ultimate strains reach to those of AFRP. The energies to peak load on both static and impact tests are maximized on the laminate constitution of A-3 that the thickness of repeating unit equals 0.6 mm and those values reach about 1.5 times as large as those of AFRP.

HYBRID EFFECT ON FLEXURAL STRENGTH

The static and impact flexural strengths of C/A hybrid FRP against laminate

constitution obtained by the maximum loads in Fig.2 are shown in Fig.6.

The symbols ● and ○ in this figure indicate respectively the compressive fracture of the most out CFRP layer in compression side of specimen, and the tensile fracture of the surface AFRP layer in tension side of specimen which are decided by observing the fracture surface of specimens after loading.

It has been already cleared that the fracture modes of CFRP laminates by the static load are the compressive fracture generated by the trigger of micro-buckling of fibers in surface layer on the compression side and that the fracture modes of AFRP laminates by the static load are the tensile fracture of the surface layer on tension side⁷. From these informations, it can be easily supposed that the fracture of C/A hybrid FRP laminate is controlled by these two fracture modes, that is the compressive fracture of CFRP layer and the tensile fracture of AFRP layer. Therefore, the flexural strengths of C/A hybrid FRP can be calculated by substituting these static and impact fracture strengths of CFRP and AFRP into the equation of laminate theory. The theoretical values of flexural strengths are given by solid and dotted lines which indicate the compressive fracture of CFRP layer and the tensile fracture of AFRP layer respectively.

The experimental data of flexural strengths are less scattering and agree fairly well with the theoretical values. The fracture modes by the experimental observation also coincide with those by the theoretical calculation. Concretely, the fracture modes of all of C series, A-1 and A-2 are the compressive fracture of the most out CFRP layer in compression side and the fracture modes of A-3 and A-4 are the tensile fracture of the surface AFRP layer in tension side. The laminate constitution of A-3 that the thickness of repeating unit equals 0.6 mm in A series maximizes the flexural strength as shown in this figure.

As the results, it was cleared that the static and impact flexural strength of C/A hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates of which the volume ratio of CFRP to AFRP is 50 % to 50 % depend fairly well on the laminate constitution, and that the laminate constitution which maximizes the flexural strength exists.

CONCLUSIONS

Carbon/aramid hybrid unidirectional reinforced FRP laminates were prepared in which the volume ratio of CFRP to AFRP was 50 % to 50 % and in which the thickness of repeating unit of CFRP and AFRP were varied. Then the static and impact three points bending tests of these C/A hybrid FRP laminates were conducted. As the results of the discussion about the effect of the laminate constitution on these strength and so on, it was found that :

- (1) The load-deflection curves of C/A hybrid FRP on the impact load are similar to those on the static load.
- (2) All types of C/A hybrid FRP which have CFRP layer on both surfaces and two types having thin AFRP layer on both surfaces fracture from the most out of CFRP layers in compression side of specimen, and the types having thick AFRP layer on both surfaces fracture from the surface of AFRP layer in tension side of specimen.
- (3) The experimental data of flexural strengths are fairly well with the theoretical values obtained by the laminate theory based on the fracture criterion above mentioned.
- (4) The flexural strengths and the energies to peak load of hybrid FRP are maximized at the laminate constitution with which the fracture mode changes.

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TABLE I Formations and properties of fibers.

	Carbon	Aramid
Diameter of mono filament (μm)	7	13
Filament number in 1 yarn	6000	1520
Elastic modulus (GPa)	235	127
Tensile strength (GPa)	3.04	2.94
Ultimate strain (%)	1.3	2.3
Specific gravity	1.77	1.45

No. of layer		Number of layer in a repeating unit (Thickness of repeating unit (mm))					
CFRP	AFRP	1 [0.2]	2 [0.4]	3 [0.6]	4 [0.8]		
8	7						
		C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4		
		7	8				
				A-1	A-2	A-3	A-4

Thickness of layer $t = 0.2 \text{ mm}$

CFRP layer AFRP layer

Fig.1 Laminate constitutions of FRP.

Fig.3 Scheme of load-deflection curve by static and impact bending test.

Fig.2 Load-deflection curves on various laminate constitutions of FRP by static and impact bending test.

Fig. 4 Comparison of flexural strength and strain in various laminate constitutions by static and impact bending test.

Fig. 5 Comparison of energy to peak load and after peak load in various laminate constitutions by static and impact bending test.

Fig. 6 Flexural strength against thickness of repeating unit by static and impact bending test.